

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' LINGUISTIC COMPETENCES.

Toshpulatova Niyoxon Shavkatjon qizi.

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute.

G.Qo'ng'urova

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Theory and methodology of education and training

(primary education) 2nd stage student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7773037>

Abstract.

This article talks about the didactic requirements for the formation of linguistic competences in students.

Keywords: linguistic competence, didactics, science, modern education, lesson, mother tongue.

It is important to pay attention to the content of education and its essence before forming linguistic competences in elementary school students. The content of education is understood as a clearly defined range of knowledge, skills and abilities that should be acquired by students in the course of studying. The essence of the educational process is to convey the historically accumulated social knowledge and experience to the younger generation, to implement interdependence between generations through a certain system. Didactic requirements are important in strengthening the educational content.

As for the explanation of this word, the word "Didactics" is derived from the Greek word "Didasco", which means "teaching, teaching". The learning object of didactics is the educational process, the development laws of the educational process, the principles, methods and forms of teaching.

In 1632, Comenius created his great pedagogical work "The Great Didactic". In this work, he uses the "idea of pan sophia" (Greek pan-whole, all, sophia-wisdom, intelligence) to know everything, to give knowledge to everyone. The school is an institution where "everyone should be taught everything", "we emphasize education for all people", he puts forward in his work.

Pedagogical scientists pay attention to the problems of the modern lesson in the course of their prohibitions and show that "a modern lesson is first of all a set of methods that teach a student to meet his educational needs independently." The teacher should not be the "Asker" and the "Speaker" in the lesson, but should closely help the students to acquire new knowledge. It is worth noting that the tasks of the teacher and students, who are its participants, have changed in modern lessons. If the teacher performs the role of a leader, guide, director, manager in the lesson, the student becomes an active participant of the lesson, he works independently, thinks and creates. One defends one's opinion in a debate, and self-management skills are formed in it.

Today, the rapid development of science is a teacher,

It is necessary to improve the activity of students, to give a new interpretation to the lessons, and to increase the effectiveness of education. At this point, it should be noted that the article "Modern lesson. How it should be" by Professor R. Jorayev published in the 1st issue of 2016 of the magazine "People's Education" as a result of the scientific bans, the achievements and

shortcomings of today's lessons were discussed in detail, and it was emphasized that scientific research is being conducted to reorganize the lessons and give them a new shape and form, and that the mask issue is one of the most urgent problems of the day.

It is known that the formation of a student as an all-round perfect person and the acquisition of high-level professional knowledge in a certain direction is closely related to the educational process. The content of education, in turn, includes the curriculum, the curriculum, and the main organizational form of education through the lesson. The lesson is an educational process that continues to this day during a very historical period, and its content and methods are being developed and refined from year to year. It is such a pedagogical process that enriches and improves content in harmony with the development of society, in each lesson the student learns something, acquires some new knowledge, and on the basis of it, desire, interest, and striving towards a certain goal appear. Also, the lesson prepares the student for the future life, that is, the student is brought up as a participant of the lesson and develops spiritually. Because the lesson is a continuous process of learning from the known to the unknown, from knowing to seeking to know again.

Another aspect of the lesson is that it serves as a basis for other forms of education, such as science competitions, trips, clubs, various thematic evenings and other activities.

Currently, elementary school textbooks are given together with the mother tongue and reading literacy, and are aimed at forming the 4 skills of students, which are defined in the speech competence, reading, writing, speaking and listening comprehension skills. The main task of elementary school mother tongue and reading classes is to prepare students for educational activities, to form a person who can communicate with others and convey his thoughts to others in an understandable way. It is important to form students' oral and written speech in primary grades. At first, oral speech is developed and thus is formed in writing.

Grammatical knowledge and skills related to speech and spelling given to students in the primary grade are considered to be thoroughly mastered only if they are used not only in some words and sentences spoken by students, but also in logically thought-out examples and essays.

. In order to develop the ability of the student to create an independent text, first of all, it is necessary to work on the development of his oral speech. Because the more the student's oral speech has developed, the more this is reflected in his written speech.

In the formation of linguistic competences in elementary school students, the lessons consist of the following:

1. Each lesson is aimed at achieving a specific goal and should be carefully planned.
2. Each lesson should have a strong ideological and political direction.
3. Each lesson should be connected with life and practice.
4. Each lesson effectively used a variety of methods, techniques and tools should be carried out.
5. Every hour and minute allocated to the lesson should be saved and used effectively.
6. In the lesson, it is necessary to make it possible to use instructional weapons, technical tools and computers related to the content of educational materials.
7. By conducting the lesson with the whole class, the individual characteristics of each student and increasing their independence are taken into account.
8. Based on the nature of the topic, in each lesson, it is necessary to look for an opportunity to refer to and use the rich pedagogical heritage of our nation.

The more attention is paid to the development of students' creative activity in the classes of the mother tongue, the easier they will perform the mental tasks set before them. As the student learns the secrets of completing assignments, he develops the ability to think creatively. Therefore, the development of linguistic competences in primary language classes not only creates conditions for students to gain deep knowledge, but also allows them to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. Therefore, every topic and task included in the mother tongue textbooks should be aimed at this goal first of all.

Summary. Opinions on the requirements for the formation of linguistic competences among students are presented. In order for the young people of today's developed new Uzbekistan to be mature and competent in all aspects, the importance of competence is considered very high.

References:

1. Toshpulatova Niyoxon Shavkatjon qizi // "The Importance of Concentration in Forming a Scientific World View in Primary Class Students" // International interdisciplinary research // 2023/1Volume2Issue1,Year2023ISSN:2835-3013 // 305-310 bet
2. Toshpo'latova Niyoxon Shavkat qizi. BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA ILMIY DUNYOQARASHNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA XALQARO BAHOLASHNING O'RNI. / Tadqiqotlar jahon ilmiy metodik jurnal/ 6-son 2-to'plam yanvar 2023. 340345-betlar.
3. R.A. Tagaynazarova. ANALYSIS OF THE PSYCHOLINGUISTIC BASIS OF TEACHING CHILDREN THEIR MOTHER TONGUE PRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD) Volume: 5 | Issue: 9 | September 2020 India - Peer Reviewed Journal.
4. Z.A. Abdunazarova. For Publication of Paper Entitled THE PLOT- THE ESSENCE OF ROLE-PLAYING GAMES AND THEIR ROLE IN TEACHING MOTHER TONGUE LESSONS In Volume 3, Issue 5 of Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal (WoS) May, 2022.
5. R.D. Norqobilova. "Determining and developing students' mother language ability as a social-pedagogical problem". JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal. Volume 8, Issue 10, Oct., 2022, Published by Novateur Publication, M.S. India. 7-10.
6. P.A. Xoliqova For Publication of Paper Entitled THE SIGNIFICANCE AND PLACE OF USING NATIONAL VALUES IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUNG GENERATION In Volume 10, Issue 11, Nov., 2022 16. D.U. Azimova "Abdullah Avloni's Pedagogical Views and its Essence" The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. 2021.
7. D. Azimova "The main Peculiarities of web tool 2 during teaching" Academic research in educational sciences, 2021. 18. Zaynab Abdunazarova. WAYS AND METHODS OF USING ROLEPLAYING GAMES IN MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES FOR THE SOCIALIZATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 3(12), 85-90. 2022/12/9 19.
8. Toshpulatova Niyoxon Shavkatjon qizi . ILMIY DUNYOQARASH VA TAFAKKURNI SHAKLLANTIRISH "INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON TEACHING, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES 2023/1" 238 -244 betlar
9. Mumunova Umida Qarshiyevna Mahmud Qoshg'ariyning "Devonu lug'otit turk" asarining pedagogika tarixida tutgan o'rni "TADDIQOTLAR" JAHON ILMIY-METODIK JURNALI (6-son, 2to'plam) 20.01.2023 YIL, 332-336 bet

10. Olloqulova Farzona Umedillayevna. Tadqiqotchilik faoliyatini shakllantirishning psixologik-pedagogik tavsifi/ Tadqiqotlar jahon ilmiy metodik jurnal/ 6-son 2-to'plam yanvar 2023. 336-339-betlar.

11. Toshpulatova Niyoxon Shavkatjon qizi// BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARIDA ILMIY DUNYOQARASHNI FANLARARO SHAKLLANTIRISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA MATEMATIKADAN SINFDAN TASHQARI ISHLARNI TASHKIL ETISH.// Proceedings of International Educators Conference Hosted online from Rome, Italy. Date: 25th January, 2023 ISSN: 2835-396X//164-170bet.

